

Supporting information

Comparison of the Tissue Distribution of a Long-Circulating Glucagon-like Peptide-1 Agonist Determined by Positron Emission Tomography and Quantitative Whole-Body Autoradiography

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Materials and Methods details

Chemicals and reagents

Standard Fmoc-protected amino acids for solid-phase peptide synthesis and OxymaPure were purchased from Gyros Protein Technologies. Pre-loaded Wang-resins were obtained from Novabiochem. *N,N'*-diisopropylcarbodiimide (DIC), piperidine, *N,N*-dimethylformamide (DMF), trifluoroacetic acid (TFA) and hexafluoroisopropanol (HFIP) were obtained from Biosolve Chemie SARL. Triisopropylsilane (TIPS), dichloromethane (DCM), *N,N*-Diisopropylethylamine (DIPEA), diethyl ether, 3,4-diethoxy-3-cyclobutene-1,2-dione, deferoxamine mesylate salt, zirconium(IV) chloride, tetrakis(triphenylphosphine)palladium(0) (Pd(PPh₃)₄), and borane dimethylamine complex (BH₃NH(CH₃)₂) were purchased from Merck.

UPLC and mass spectrometric analysis for chemical synthesis

Purified peptides were analysed by mass spectrometry on a RP-UPLC-MS system in positive ion mode using electrospray ionization (Waters Acquity UPLC H Class equipped with Waters Acquity BEH C-18 column, 1.7μm, 2.1 x 50 mm and Waters Xevo G2-XS QToF detector). MassLynx V4.2 software was used for analyzing the mass spectra. The purity of the peptides was determined by analytical RP-UPLC (Waters Acquity UPLC H Class) using an analytical C18 column (Waters Acquity BEH, C-18 column, 1.7μm, 2.1 x 150 mm) and a linear gradient of 5–95% solvent B (MeCN, 0.05% [v/v] TFA) in solvent A (H₂O, 0.05% [v/v] TFA) in 16 minutes at a flow rate of 0.4 ml min⁻¹. The column temperature was 40°C and absorbance was detected at 220 nm (Waters Acquity PDA Detector).

Synthesis of peptide and precursors

Solid-phase peptide synthesis was performed on a SymphonyX automated synthesizer (Gyros Protein Technologies) using standard Fmoc protocols. Wang resin pre-loaded with the C-terminal amino acid was used as solid support. Peptide couplings were carried out by reacting amino acid (4

eq) with OxymaPure (4eq) and DIC (4 eq) in DMF. *N*-terminal Fmoc protecting groups were removed using 20% piperidine in DMF. Fmoc-Lys(Mtt)-OH was used in position 37 (GLP-1 numbering) for selective incorporation of the fatty acid side chain. After assembly of the complete peptide sequence, the Mtt side chain protecting group was selectively deprotected by treatment with HFIP/TIPS/DCM (75:2.5:22.5%) for 30 min. The free amine was then reacted with the succinimidyl-ester of the fatty acid side chain (6 eq) using DIPEA (10 eq) in DMF. Final deprotection and cleavage from the resin were done in a cleavage cocktail containing TFA/water/TIPS (95/2.5/2.5%) for 1.5 h. The resin was removed by filtration and peptides precipitated in ice-cold diethyl ether. The precipitate was pelleted by centrifugation and washed twice with diethyl ether. Peptides were purified using a RP-HPLC system equipped with a preparative C18 column (Phenomenex Gemini 5 μ m NX C18 110Å, 30 x 250 mm). Fractions containing the desired compound were pooled and lyophilized to yield the peptides as fluffy, white powders.

Synthesis of peptides 1 and 2

Peptide 1

Peptide 1 was prepared as previously described [1]. UPLC analysis traces are described in Figure S11.

Peptide 2

Peptide **2** was prepared as previously described [1]. UPLC analysis traces are described in Figure S11.

Synthesis of peptide precursors for tritium labeling

The precursor peptides **3** and **4**, used in the synthesis of tritiated peptides [3H]**1** and [3H]**2** respectively, were synthesised following the same solid-phase peptide synthesis strategy as described for peptides **1** and **2** but absent of the fatty acid and the DFO motifs.

Peptide 3

The C-terminal residue lysine-37 was used to conjugate [3H]-labeled fatty acid sidechain and was incorporated containing the side-chain amine Boc-protected using the commercial amino acid precursor Fmoc-Lys(Boc)-OH. After the coupling of all the remaining amino acids, the peptide was cleaved using a mixture containing TFA/water/TIPS (95/2.5/2.5%) for 1.5 h. The resin was removed

by filtration and peptides precipitated in ice-cold diethyl ether. The precipitate was pelleted by centrifugation and washed twice with diethyl ether. Peptides were purified using a RP-HPLC system equipped with a preparative C18 column (Phenomenex Gemini 5 μm NX C18 110 \AA , 30 x 250 mm). Fractions containing the desired compound were pooled and lyophilized to yield the peptides as a fluffy, white powder. UPLC analysis traces are described in Figure S11.

Peptide 4

For **4**, the lysine to be tritiated (Lys37), was incorporated as the Fmoc-Lys(Alloc)-OH and the lysine to be conjugated to the DFO chelator (Lys41) was incorporated as a Fmoc-Lys(Boc)-OH derivative. After standard cleavage and purification of the Alloc-protected peptide, DFO conjugation, Alloc deprotection and zirconium chelation were performed in a one-pot three-step reaction without intermediate purification as follows: The purified, Alloc protected peptide was dissolved in sodium bicarbonate buffer (0.1M, pH 11) and MeCN (20%). For conjugation of the DFO to Lys41, DFO squaramide ester (3 eq) was added and the reaction stirred for 2 h at 50 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. The reaction mix was then diluted with acetic acid and the Alloc protecting group on Lys37 was removed by $\text{Pd}(\text{PPh}_3)_4$ (0.2 eq in degassed DCM) and $\text{BH}_3\text{NH}(\text{CH}_3)_2$ (15 eq in degassed DCM) under nitrogen atmosphere overnight. The peptide was then precipitated in ice-cold diethyl ether and re-dissolved in sodium bicarbonate

buffer (0.1M, pH 9). Aqueous $ZrCl_4$ (4 eq) was added to the peptide. Full chelation was observed after 5 min and the desired product **4** was purified by RP-HPLC as above. UPLC analysis traces are described in Figure S11.

Radiosynthesis of the succinimidyl ester precursor [3H]5

The radiolabeling of the succinimidyl ester precursor [3H]5 was done as previously described with minor modifications [2]. The radiosynthesis was done on a tritium manifold (RC Tritech). 9.5 mg (9.5 μ mol) of the benzyl ester starting material was dissolved in 0.8 mL of NMP. To this mixture, 6.6 mg 10% Pd/C and 5 μ L of TFA was added. The reaction was placed on the tritium manifold, frozen in liquid nitrogen and evacuated to 3×10^{-3} mbar. Tritium gas was placed over the reaction at 465 mbar. The reaction was left for 3 hours during which the pressure over the reaction lowered to 400 mbar. The mixture was lyophilized from 70% ethanol in water on the manifold three times to remove dissolved tritium gas. After this 4.0 mL of NMP was added to a total volume of 4.8 mL. The total activity was measured by liquid scintillation counting to be 331 mCi (12.2 GBq) and the product had a radiochemical purity of 48%.

Synthesis of peptide precursor **6** for zirconium-89 labeling

Peptide **6** was prepared as previously described [1]. UPLC analysis traces are described in Figure S11.

DFO conjugation

The DFO conjugation was performed using a purified peptide precursor containing a C-terminal lysine residue. The peptide was dissolved in sodium bicarbonate buffer (0.1M, pH 11) and MeCN (20%). DFO squaramide ester (DFOSq) was prepared from 3,4-diethoxy-3-cyclobutene-1,2-dione and deferoxamine mesylate salt as previously described [29]. Three equivalents of DFOSq were added and the reaction stirred for 2 h at 50°C. The reaction was quenched with aqueous TFA and purified by RP-HPLC.

Non-radioactive zirconium chelation

The reaction mix containing the precursor peptide was diluted with sodium bicarbonate buffer and the pH adjusted to 9. Aqueous ZrCl₄ (4 eq) was added to the reaction mix. Full chelation was observed after 5 min by LC-MS. The desired product was purified by RP-HPLC.

Peptide concentration determination

Peptides were quantified by Charged Aerosol Detection (CAD) on a LC-CAD system (Thermo-Fisher Vanquish) using an analytical C18 column (Waters CSH C-18, 130Å, 1.7 μm, 2.1 x 50 mm) and a linear gradient of 0–80% solvent B (MeCN, 0.1% [v/v] TFA) in solvent A (H₂O, 0.1% [v/v] TFA) over 4 minutes at a flow rate of 0.3 ml min⁻¹. Quantification was performed using the signal from a CAD detector (Thermo-Fisher Vanquish Charged Aerosol Detector H) calibrated using insulin aspartate as an external standard.

Pharmacokinetic analysis

Animals and welfare

Animal experiments were done following the Danish animal welfare authorization (2014-15-0201-00388: C02) and Novo Nordisk's internal ethical committee. 18 Sprague Dawley rats were used, housed at 4 animals per cage and weighted 225-250 g. Animals were acclimatized for at least a week

before the experiments, maintained at 12 h light-dark cycle with water and food (Altromin) ad libitum and dosed at a maximum 1 mL/kg.

Dosing and plasma sampling

Animals received the compounds at a 20 nmol/kg dose intravenously or subcutaneously. Six 200 μ L blood samples were taken at 2, 6, 10, 24, 30 and 48 h in lithium/heparin tubes. Blood samples were kept on ice, centrifuged (5 min, 8000 rpm) and plasma was transferred to a cryotube and kept at -80°C until analysis.

Sample extraction and analysis

25 μ L of plasma was mixed with 50 μ L of a MeCN/MeOH (4/1, v/v) solution chilled to -20°C , mixed and centrifuged (16000 g, 10 min, 4°C). 40 μ L of the supernatant was mixed with 80 μ L of deionized water, vortexed and analysed by UPLC-MS using a BEH C18 column using the following analytical methods:

UPLC-MS analytical methods for pharmacokinetic analysis of 1 and 2.

Column	ACQUITY UPLC Peptide BEH C18, 300Å, 1.7 μm , 2.1x150mm		
Mobile phase A	1% formic acid in water		
Mobile phase B	1% formic acid in acetonitrile		
Gradient	Time (min)	%A	%B
	0	95	5
	1	70	30
	6	30	70
	8	20	80
	10	0	100
	10.1	95	5
	15	95	5

Flow rate	0.4 ml/min
Run time	50 min
Temperature	50°C (column oven)
Injection volume	10 uL
Detection	MS

MS

MS tune – ES+	Capillary voltage	1.0 kV
	Sampling cone	60
	Source offset	80
	Source temperature	150°C
	Desolvation temperature	500°C
	Desolvation gas flow	1000 l/h
	Nebuliser gas flow	6.5
MS method –Acquisition	Start and end times (min)	0 and 15
	Analyser mode	Resolution
MS method – Method events	Initial condition	Flow State – LC - Sample
MS method – TOF MS/MS	Polarity (ion mode)	Positive
	Scan time	0.5 sec
	Data format	Continuum
	Transition 1	1062.9 (2)
	Transition 2	1064.8 (1)

Peptide tritiation

Radiosynthesis of [³H]**1** and [³H]**2** proceeded by conjugating the corresponding non-radioactive peptide precursors (peptides **3** and **4**, respectively) to a tritiated fatty acid succinimidyl ester ([³H]**5**) at position Lys37. 1200 nmol of the peptide precursors were dissolved in 1.2 mL of NMP and mixed

with 325 μL of triethylamine (2.3 mmol). Then, 1.8 mL of the tritiated fatty acid [^3H]5 (4.6 GBq) was added to each peptide precursor solution and stirred for 15 min at room temperature. The reaction was quenched with 5 mL of 3% TFA in water. The mixtures were diluted with 5.0 mL of water and purified by semipreparative HPLC with a C18 column (Waters Symmetry prep), running a gradient of 35-60% B buffer (acetonitrile with 0.1% TFA) in A buffer (MilliQ water with 0.1% TFA) over 25 minutes; flow 5.0 mL/min. Analysis was performed on a UPLC with a ACQUITY UPLC Peptide CSH C18 Column, 130 \AA , 1,7 μm , 2,1 x 150 mm column running a gradient 5-95% B buffer (acetonitrile with 0.1% TFA) in A buffer (MilliQ water with 0.1% TFA) over 20 minutes; flow 0.35 mL/min. The radiochemical purity was determined by UPLC with scintillation detection (Berthold LCS). The selected purified fractions were pooled, diluted to 20% acetonitrile by addition of water, and concentrated using a Waters C18 Sep-pack and eluted in 2.5 mL 70% ethanol in water. These solutions were analysed and subsequently stored at $-80\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. The specific activity was determined from a fitted standard curve and confirmed by mass spectrometry. The amount of radioactivity was determined by liquid scintillation counting.

Tritiated peptides chemical characterization

Peptide [^3H]1

Mass (for the corresponding specific activity)	$[M+4H]^{+4}$: Calculated: 1065.4 Found: 1065.5
Amount	4.0 mCi = 148 MBq
Radiochemical purity	97% (Day 0)
Molar activity	29.0 Ci/mmol = 1073 GBq/mmol

Formulation analysis (Pre-dose)

Dose Group	Peptide	Measured Peptide		
		Radioactivity concentration (MBq/mL)	concentration (nmol/mL)	Purity (%)
B	$[^3H]1$	32.9	30.6	95.1

Peptide [³H]2

Mass (for the corresponding specific activity)	[M+5H] ⁺ : Calculated: 1063.6 Found: 1063.7
Amount	3.9 mCi = 144 MBq
Radiochemical purity	92% (Day 0)
Specific activity	29.0 Ci/mmol = 1073 GBq/mmol

Formulation analysis (Pre-dose)

Dose Group	Peptide	Measured	Peptide	Purity (%)
		Radioactivity concentration (MBq/mL)	concentration (nmol/mL)	
A	[³ H]2	33.6	31.3	93.1
C	[³ H]2	31.6	29.4	92.2

Tritium Quantitative whole-body autoradiography

Animals and welfare

Compound dosing, plasma sampling and whole-body autoradiography of tritiated peptides were done at contract laboratory facilities (LabCorp Laboratories, Harrogate, UK). All animal experiments and welfare monitoring were conducted according to United Kingdom animal welfare law, in particular, the Animals Act of 1986 (License number: PPL P61F851DB). In total 21 Sprague Dawley, male rats were used weighing 220 ± 20 g (7-9 weeks old). Animals were housed up to 5 individuals per cage and temperature and humidity were maintained at 19-25 °C and 40-70%, respectively. Animals were acclimatized for at least seven days on a 12 h light-dark cycle and allowed free access to water and food. Animals were dosed at a maximum 1 mL/kg.

Dosing and detailed QWBA procedure

Peptides [³H]1 and [³H]2 were formulated at a final concentration of 30 nmol/mL in a pH = 7.4 vehicle containing 50 mM phosphate buffer, 70 mM NaCl and 70 ppm Tween 20. Animals received one single i.v or s.c administration of peptides dosed at 30 nmol/kg (32 MBq/kg). Animals in group A (n= 5) received peptide [³H]2, s.c; animals in group B (n= 5) received peptide [³H]1, s.c; animals in group C (n= 5) received peptide [³H]2, i.v. One animal (group D, n=1) received vehicle at 1 mL/Kg. Following dosing, the animals returned to the cages and were killed at 4, 8, 24, 72 and 168

h by freezing on a hexane/dry ice mixture (-80 °C) under isoflurane anesthesia (n = 1 per time point). After at least 30 min under freezing temperature, the legs, tail, and whiskers were trimmed off from each frozen carcass before freezing into a block of aqueous 2% (w/v) carboxymethylcellulose. Longitudinal, sagittal sections (30 µm) were taken onto Filmolux 610 tape and exposed to Fuji Imaging Plates (type BAS TR2040) for 14 days. Images were obtained using a Typhoon radioluminography system (GE Healthcare, USA). Whole-body autoradiograms were analysed using a validated PC-based image analysis package (Seescan software, LabLogic Systems Ltd). The sites of tissue accumulation of radioactivity were identified by visual inspection of the autoradiograms and quantified by reference to calibration curves.

Metabolite profiling

Plasma sampling

Terminal blood samples were collected at 4, 8, 24, 72 and 168 hours post-dose. The animals, still under anesthesia, were taken up 3 mL of blood by cardiac puncture into blood tubes containing anticoagulant (sodium citrate, 3.2%). After aliquoting a portion of whole blood for radio-analysis the remainder was centrifuged (1500 g, 10 min, 4°C) to obtain plasma and stored at -80°C until analysis. For peptide [³H]**2** after i.v administration additional time points of 5 min and 2 h were collected non-terminally and pooled (n= 5). For this, *ca.* 250 µL of blood was taken into blood tubes containing anticoagulant (sodium citrate; 3.2%). The bleed site was swabbed clean before each withdrawal of blood. After centrifugation (1500 g, 10 min, 4°C), plasma was obtained and stored at -80°C until analysis.

Sample extraction and HPLC analysis for metabolic profiling

200 μL of each plasma sample was transferred to a low-bind plastic tube containing 200 μL of a cold (5 $^{\circ}\text{C}$) mixture of 25% methanol in acetonitrile. Samples were vortexed and centrifuged (12500g, 15 min, 4 $^{\circ}\text{C}$), 300 μL of the supernatant is transferred to a HPLC vial containing 150 μL of deionized water and vortexed. Extraction recoveries were measured by scintillation counting and were higher than 85% (Table S10). 300 μL of the extracted samples were injected and analysed by an Ultimate 3000 HPLC (Thermo Scientific, USA), using a XBridge (BEH C18, 300A, 5 μm , 250 mm, 4.6 mm) column at 40 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. The mobile phase was composed of A: 3% formic acid in water; B: 3% formic acid, 1% water in acetonitrile. A constant flow of 1 mL/min of the following linear gradient was used: 0 min, 5% B; 45 min, 60%B; 50 min, 100%B, 75 min 100%B, 76 min, 5%B. The HPLC was coupled to a scintillation detector (ARC2, AIM Research, USA) via a UCI-50 interface. The HPLC eluent: scintillation fluid (Ultima-Flo M, PerkinElmer, USA) rate was 1:2.5 .

Scintillation counting

50 μL of sample (plasma or extracted solution) was mixed with 3 mL of scintillation fluid (Ultima Gold, PerkinElmer, USA), vortex and counted on a Tri-Carb 2910 TR) for 5 min on a plastic scintillation tube.

Metabolite identification

Sample preparation

For metabolic identification 250 μL of plasma samples from animals dosed after 8, 24 and 72 h with peptide [^3H]2 were pooled and mixed with 750 μL of cold (5 $^{\circ}\text{C}$) 25% methanol in acetonitrile, vortexed and centrifuged (12500g, 15 min, 4 $^{\circ}\text{C}$). Approx. 1.4 mL of the supernatant solution was transferred to a low bind plastic vial and evaporated (under N_2 , 36 $^{\circ}\text{C}$) until approx. 700 μL was left. This solution was centrifugated and the supernatant transferred to a new vial and analysed using the same instrument and analytical method as in metabolic profiling. The HPLC solvent outlet was diverted to a fraction collector, and samples were collected in 2 mL 96-well plates (0.25 mL fractions).

Fractions from two HPLC injections were collected into the same 96 well plates. Radioactivity levels in each fraction were determined by transferring 30 μL of each collected fraction to a new 96-well plate (Lumaplate, PerkinElmer, USA) and reading on a TopCount NXT/HTS plate-reader (PerkinElmer, USA). Fractions containing the metabolite of interest were transferred to a low-binding vial, dried to approx. half of the original volume (under N_2 , 36 $^\circ\text{C}$) and selected for UPLC-MS-RAD analysis.

A second sample preparation method was used for analysis of the crude plasma, without fractionation and sample drying. In this, 100 μL of plasma from the animal dosed subcutaneously with [^3H]2, time point 24 h was added with 200 μL of cold ($-20\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) 25% methanol in acetonitrile, vortexed and centrifuged (5000g, 5 min, 4°C). 200 μL of the supernatant was transferred to a low-binding vial containing 500 μL of water, mixed and analysed directly by UPLC-MS-RAM. Plasma samples from non-dosed animals were subjected to the same sample preparation procedures described above and used as control matrices during the assignment of possible metabolites.

UPLC-MS-RAM

UPLC-MS-RAM analysis was conducted with Acquity I-Class UPLC (Waters, USA) connected in-line with a time-of-flight Synapt G2-S mass spectrometer (Waters, USA) and a v.ARC (AIM Research, USA) radioactivity detector, using an Acquity UPLC Peptide BEH C18, 300 \AA , 1.7 μm , 2.1x150mm column. Data processing was done with MassLynx software (Waters, USA, v. 4.1) and mass deconvolution using the MaxEnt3 algorithm.

UPLC-MS-RAM analytical methods for metabolite identification

UPLC-MS-RAM method for samples obtained after fractionation

Column	ACQUITY UPLC Peptide CSH C18, 300 \AA , 1.7 μm , 2.1x150mm
Mobile phase A	1% formic acid in water

Mobile phase B	1% formic acid in acetonitrile		
Gradient	Time (min)	%A	%B
	0	95	5
	5	95	5
	10	70	30
	40	55	45
	40.1	0	100
	45	0	100
	45.1	95	5
Flow rate	0.4 ml/min		
Run time	50 min		
Temperature	50°C (column oven)		
Injection volume	9 dummy injections of 10 uL, followed by 10 uL injection run		
Detection	MS and ARC		

MS and ARC

MS tune – ES+	Capillary voltage	2.5 kV
	Sampling cone	40
	Source offset	80
	Source temperature	120°C
	Desolvation temperature	250°C
	Desolvation gas flow	800 l/h
	Nebuliser gas flow	6.0
MS method –Acquisition	Start and end times (min)	0 and 50
	Analyser mode	Resolution
MS method – Method events	Initial condition	Flow State – LC - Sample

MS method – TOF MS	Polarity (ion mode)	Positive
	Scan time	1 sec
	Data format	Continuum
	Low and High mass	500 and 2000 Da
Scintillation detection system	v.ARC	
Detection method	Dynamic flow	
Scintillation fluid	Ultima-flo M (PerkinElmer)	

UPLC-MS-RAM method for samples obtained without fractionation

Column	ACQUITY UPLC Peptide CSH C18, 300Å, 1.7 um, 2.1x150mm		
Mobile phase A	1% formic acid in water		
Mobile phase B	1% formic acid in acetonitrile		
Gradient	Time (min)	%A	%B
	0	95	5
	5.1	68	32
	40	62	38
	40.1	0	100
	45	0	100
	45.1	95	5
Flow rate	0.4 ml/min		
Run time	50 min		
Temperature	50°C		
Injection volume	4 dummy injections of 10 uL, followed by 10 uL injection run		
Detection	MS and ARC		

MS and ARC

MS tune – ES+	Capillary voltage	3.0 kV
	Sampling cone	40°C
	Source offset	80 °C
	Source temperature	80°C
	Desolvation temperature	150 °C
	Desolvation gas flow	600 l/h
	Nebuliser gas flow	6.5 Bar
	Trap Collision Energy	4

	Transfer Collision Energy	4
MS method –Acquisition	Start and end times (min)	0 and 50
	Analyser mode	Resolution
MS method – Method events	Initial condition	Flow State – LC - Sample
MS method – TOF MS	Polarity (ion mode)	Positive
	Scan time	1 sec
	Data format	Continuum
	Low and High mass	500 and 2000 Da
Scintillation detection system	v.ARC	
Detection method	Dynamic flow	
Scintillation fluid	Ultima-flo M (PerkinElmer)	

Zirconium-89 radiolabeling

Radiosynthesis of [⁸⁹Zr]2 was done according to a previously published procedure [29]. Briefly, the peptide precursor **6** containing the deferoxamine chelator was mixed with [⁸⁹Zr]Zr(oxalate)₂ solution (PerkinElmer, Netherlands) and the pH was adjusted to 7.8 with a 0.2 M solution of bicarbonate buffer. The reaction proceeded for 2 h at room temperature and the radiolabeling efficacy was >95% as evaluated by instant thin layer TLC (sialic acid impregnated stationary phase, ammonium acetate/EDTA solution in water as mobile phase). The molar activity was set to 5 MBq/nmol.

Biodistribution of zirconium-89 labeled peptides and PET imaging

Animals and welfare

Animal studies were approved by the Dutch committee on animal research and the local ethical committee of the Radboud University (Protocol 2017-0028). 30 Sprague Dawley rats (Envigo, Netherlands) weighing 250-300 g were acclimatized for at least 4 days before the experiment started.

Animals had free access to water and food and were housed in a 12 h light-dark cycle (22 °C, 10-55 % humidity). Rats were randomly allocated to the experimental groups according to a random sequence generator.

Table S1. Pharmacokinetic parameters of **1** after intravenous administration

Subject	Dose	Bodyweight	C ₀	AUC	AUC/Dose	AUC		Lambda Z	t _{1/2}	MRT	Cl	Vz
						Extrapolated	(%)					
8	18235	0.306	529000	5174302	284	3.6	0.0637	10.9	12.9	0.003524	0.055305	

Table S2. Pharmacokinetic parameters of **1** after subcutaneous administration

Subject	Dose	Bodyweight	T _{max}	C _{max}	AUC	AUC/Dose	AUC		Lambda Z	t _{1/2}	Cl/F	Vz/F	F
							Extrapolated	(%)					
13	18059	0.304	10	62510	1797806	99.6	10	0.0566	12.2	0.010045	0.177474	35.1	
14	18058	0.309	10	64348	2124297	118	8.5	0.0649	10.7	0.008501	0.130978	41.5	
15	17872	0.282	10	69445	2036757	114	21.2	0.0373	18.6	0.006912	0.185481	40.1	
16	18052	0.349	10	60350	1956737	108	12.2	0.0539	12.9	0.009225	0.171176	38.0	
Mean*	18010	0.311	10	64163	1978899	109.9	12.98	0.0532	13.0	0.008671	0.166277	38.7	
SD	92	0.028		3882	138773	8.0	5.69	0.0116	18.6]	0.001331	0.024250	2.8	

*Harmonic mean for t_{1/2}, t_{max} is median and arithmetic mean for remaining parameters

Table S3. Pharmacokinetic parameters of **2** after intravenous administration

Subject	Dose	Bodyweight	C ₀	AUC	AUC/Dose	AUC		Lambda Z	t _{1/2}	MRT	Cl	Vz
						Extrapolated	(%)					
1	17838	0.333	276000	2392988	134	1.7	0.0815	8.5	10.9	0.007454	0.091472	
2	17881	0.302	393000	2527663	141	1.1	0.0863	8	9	0.007074	0.081953	
3	17833	0.323	407000	2766412	155	1.6	0.0804	8.6	10.1	0.006446	0.080212	
Mean*	17851	0.319	358667	2562354	143	1.47	0.0827	8.4	10.0	0.006991	0.084546	
SD	26	0.016	71933	189114	11	0.32	0.0031	[8-9.1]	1.0	0.000509	0.006061	

*Harmonic mean for t_{1/2}, t_{max} is median and arithmetic mean for remaining parameters

Table S4. Pharmacokinetic parameters of **2** after subcutaneous administration

Subject	Dose	Bodyweight	T _{max}	C _{max}	AUC	AUC/Dose	AUC		Lambda Z	t _{1/2}	Cl/F	Vz/F	F
							Extrapolated	(%)					
4	17941	0.306	6	70674	1402621	78.2	2.1	0.09	7.7	0.012791	0.142144	54.6	
5	18000	0.28	6	66147	1362478	75.7	2.3	0.0872	7.9	0.013211	0.151431	52.8	
6	17890	0.327	10	49499	1010056	56.5	3.1	0.0796	8.7	0.017712	0.222496	39.4	
7	18117	0.308	10	56783	1467862	81	4.1	0.0807	8.6	0.012342	0.153031	56.5	
Mean*	17987	0.305	8	60776	1310754	72.9	2.90	0.0844	8.2	0.014014	0.167276	50.8	
SD	98	0.019		9486	205116	11.1	0.91	0.0050	8.7]	0.002491	0.037125	7.8	

*Harmonic mean for t_{1/2}, t_{max} is median and arithmetic mean for remaining parameters

Table S5. Ex-vivo biodistribution of [⁸⁹Zr]2 after intravenous administration

Tissue	Uptake in tissue (%ID/ g)							
	4 h		24 h		72 h		168 h	
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD
Kidney	4.75	0.56	8.27	0.58	8.56	1.17	7.15	2
Lung	1.91	0.23	1.49	0.13	1.09	0.25	1.02	0.36
Blood	1.21	0.06	0.23	0.04	0.04	0.01	0.03	0.02
Liver	1.02	0.05	1.1	0.19	0.91	0.15	0.69	0.23
Bone marrow	0.94	0.22	0.99*	0.16	0.49	0.13	1.24	1.31
Stomach-duodenum	0.49	0.05	0.47	0.07	0.44	0.12	0.41	0.06
Skin neck	0.48	0.04	0.31	0.07	0.18	0.02	0.17	0.05
Heart	0.47	0.06	0.16	0.02	0.11	0.01	0.09	0.02
Colon	0.43	0.1	0.26	0.06	0.2	0.02	0.17	0.04
Spleen	0.38	0.03	0.49	0.06	0.46	0.08	0.53	0.18
Stomach	0.34	0.04	0.31	0.05	0.22	0.06	0.17	0.05
Intestine	0.31	0.04	0.19	0.08	0.14	0.03	0.12	0.02
Knee	0.3	0.02	0.23	0.01	0.22	0.02	0.26	0.06
Pancreas	0.3	0.05	0.2	0.03	0.32	0.16	0.11**	0.03
Duodenum	0.29	0.04	0.2	0.05	0.17	0.03	0.15	0.02
Content of intestine	0.27	0.06	0.07	0.03	0.06	0.02	0.03	0.01
Skin injection	0.25	0.03	0.16	0.03	0.1	0.02	0.1	0.03
Femur	0.17	0.02	0.15	0.02	0.14	0.01	0.18	0.05
Content of stomach/duodenum	0.13	0.05	0.09	0.05	0.05	0.02	0.04	0.01
Content of duodenum	0.13	0.01	0.07	0.03	0.03	0.01	0.03	0.01
Muscle	0.12	0.01	0.07	0.02	0.04	0.01	0.05	0.03
Brain	0.05	0.01	0.02	0	0.01	0	0.01	0
Colon content	0.01	0	0.24	0.07	0.1	0.03	0.05	0.02

*n = 5. ** n = 2. n = 6 for all other tissues

Table S6. Ex-vivo biodistribution of [⁸⁹Zr]2 after subcutaneous administration

Tissue	Uptake in tissue (%ID/ g)							
	4 h		24 h		72 h		168 h	
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD
Skin injection	5.14	4.09	2.13	2.24	1.32	2.07	0.5	0.31
Kidney	1.39	0.2	5.82	1.12	6.57	0.95	5.17	1.62
Lung	1.02	0.16	1.33	0.32	0.85	0.26	0.73	0.25
Bone marrow	0.97	0.46	1.01	0.82	0.38	0.21	0.53	0.18
Blood	0.66	0.1	0.3	0.02	0.04	0.01	0.02	0.01
Liver	0.37	0.07	0.75	0.1	0.64	0.1	0.45	0.21
Heart	0.2	0.03	0.14	0.02	0.07	0.01	0.06	0.01
Stomach-duodenum	0.18	0.07	0.37	0.07	0.3	0.11	0.28	0.06
Colon	0.18	0.04	0.21	0.04	0.14	0.05	0.11	0.03
Skin neck	0.17	0.04	0.27	0.03	0.14	0.05	0.1	0.04
Duodenum	0.15	0.02	0.18	0.04	0.11	0.04	0.11	0.02
Content of stomach/duodenum	0.13	0.11	0.12	0.06	0.05	0.02	0.04	0.01
Intestine	0.13	0.02	0.16	0.04	0.1	0.04	0.09	0.02
Pancreas	0.13	0.03	0.16	0.03	0.18	0.09	0.08*	0.01
Spleen	0.12	0.01	0.27	0.06	0.27	0.05	0.3	0.11
Stomach	0.12	0.01	0.22	0.05	0.15	0.05	0.13	0.05
Knee	0.12	0.02	0.21	0.09	0.18	0.03	0.22	0.03
Content of intestine	0.09	0.01	0.11	0.04	0.05	0.02	0.02	0.01
Content of duodenum	0.08	0.02	0.08	0.04	0.03	0.02	0.02	0.01
Femur	0.08	0.02	0.12	0.03	0.11	0.01	0.14	0.02
Muscle	0.06	0.02	0.07	0.02	0.08	0.07	0.04	0.02
Brain	0.03	0.01	0.02	0	0.01	0.01	0	0
Colon content	0.01	0.01	0.24	0.06	0.07	0.01	0.05	0.02

*n = 3. n = 6 for all other tissues

Table S7. Tissue uptake (percentage of injected dose per gram of tissue, %ID/g) from quantitative whole-body autoradiography of [³H]2 after 4, 8, 24, 72 and 168 h of intravenous administration (30 nmol/kg). n = 1.

Tissue	% ID /g				
	4 h	8 h	24 h	72 h	168 h
Adrenal cortex	1.04	0.43	0.15	0.04	NA
Adrenal medulla	3.86	1.42	0.79	0.07	NA
Aortic wall	1.15	0.98	0.25	0.04	NA
Bile ducts	4.63	3.77	1.30	0.11	NA
Blood	5.66	3.32	1.08	0.09	NA
Blood ¹	4.31	2.87	1.16	0.22	0.08
Bone marrow	0.77	0.77	0.19	0.03	NA
Bone mineral	0.11	0.03	NA	NA	NA
Bone surface	0.58	0.87	0.25	0.05	NA
Brain (cerebellum)	0.14	0.07	0.03	NA	NA
Brain (cortex)	0.09	0.05	0.03	NA	NA
Brain (medulla oblongata)	0.05	0.05	0.02	NA	NA
Brain (olfactory bulb)	0.05	0.03	0.02	NA	NA
Brain (thalamus)	0.06	0.04	0.03	NA	NA
Brain (whole)	0.09	0.05	0.02	NA	NA
Brown fat	0.32	0.14	0.09	0.02	NA
Bulbo-urethral gland	0.91	0.68	0.53	0.09	NA
Caecum mucosa	0.98	0.46	0.17	0.05	NA
Cartilage	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
Cerebrospinal fluid	4.16	4.95	1.63	0.12	NA
Choroid plexus	3.52	0.93	0.12	0.10	NA
Colon mucosa	0.76	0.48	0.25	0.03	NA
Epididymis	0.67	1.22	0.36	0.06	NA
Epimysium	0.68	0.78	0.39	0.04	NA
Epithelial tongue	0.91	0.79	0.55	0.03	NA
Exorbital lachrymal gland	0.38	0.33	0.23	0.03	NA
Hair (follicle)	0.85	0.44	0.22	0.05	NA
Hair (tactile)	2.43	1.38	0.80	0.06	NA
Harderian gland	0.20	0.12	0.13	0.03	NA
Intra-orbital lachrymal gland	0.28	0.28	0.15	0.02	NA
Kidney (CM Junction)	5.58	4.15	4.29	0.65	0.05
Kidney cortex	5.73	4.57	1.95	0.29	0.04
Kidney medulla	2.22	1.42	0.38	0.04	0.02
Lens	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA

Liver	1.04	0.65	0.46	0.05	NA
Lung	4.38	2.77	1.07	0.08	NA
Lymph nodes	0.56	0.68	0.20	0.02	NA
Meninges	0.80	0.50	0.17	0.02	NA
Mucus gland	0.83	0.62	0.27	0.05	NA
Muscle	0.23	0.29	0.15	0.02	NA
Myocardium	1.07	0.57	0.22	0.03	NA
Nasal mucosa	0.55	0.40	0.16	0.02	NA
Oesophageal wall	1.05	0.87	0.35	0.05	NA
Pancreas	0.89	0.80	0.22	0.04	NA
Penis	1.10	1.54	0.99	0.09	NA
Periodontal membrane	4.17	1.85	1.04	0.06	NA
Pineal body	1.20	0.52	0.16	0.03	NA
Pituitary	0.83	0.56	0.22	0.04	NA
Plasma FD ¹	6.75	4.59	1.83	0.13	0.01
Plasma ¹	6.82	4.70	2.08	0.41	0.12
Preputial gland	0.23	0.16	0.08	0.04	NA
Prostate	0.36	0.94	0.15	0.03	NA
Salivary glands	1.18	0.54	0.19	0.04	NA
Seminal vesicles	0.13	0.14	0.04	0.02	NA
Skin (non-pigmented)	0.29	0.30	0.23	0.03	NA
Skin (subcutis)	0.82	0.96	0.32	0.06	NA
Small intestine mucosa	0.92	0.56	0.24	NA	NA
Spinal cord	0.06	0.04	0.02	NA	NA
Spleen	0.61	0.39	0.17	0.02	NA
Stomach mucosa (fundic)	0.45	0.30	0.26	0.02	NA
Stomach mucosa (non-fundic)	0.60	0.48	0.18	0.03	NA
Testis	0.66	0.68	0.24	0.02	NA
Thymus	0.33	0.23	0.12	0.03	NA
Thyroid	1.33	0.89	0.32	0.05	NA
Tongue	0.85	0.97	0.52	0.06	NA
Tooth pulp	5.48	2.81	1.61	0.13	NA
Trachea	1.07	0.83	0.27	0.08	NA
Urinary bladder wall	1.01	1.09	0.72	0.08	NA
Uveal tract/retina	0.88	1.31	0.53	0.05	NA
Vitreous humour	0.02	NA	NA	NA	NA
White fat	0.06	0.03	0.02	NA	NA

1 – Counts determined by liquid scintillation; NA- below limit of quantification; FD – freeze-dried before measurement.

Table S8. Tissue uptake (percentage of injected dose per gram of tissue, %ID/g) from quantitative whole-body autoradiography of [³H]2 after 4, 8, 24, 72 and 168 h of subcutaneous administration (30 nmol/kg). n = 1.

Tissue	% ID /g				
	4 h	8 h	24 h	72 h	168 h
Adrenal cortex	0.17	0.28	0.20	0.06	NA
Adrenal medulla	0.50	1.18	0.65	0.06	NA
Aortic wall	0.11	0.74	0.38	0.04	NA
Bile ducts	1.37	1.76	1.89	0.18	NA
Blood	1.07	1.63	1.38	0.14	NA
Blood1	0.95	1.53	1.35	0.28	0.01
Bone marrow	0.27	0.24	0.32	0.04	NA
Bone mineral	0.02	0.02	0.03	0.02	NA
Bone surface	0.28	0.29	0.25	0.07	NA
Brain (cerebellum)	0.03	0.03	0.04	NA	NA
Brain (cortex)	0.02	0.02	0.03	NA	NA
Brain (medulla oblongata)	0.02	0.02	0.02	NA	NA
Brain (olfactory bulb)	0.02	0.02	0.03	NA	NA
Brain (thalamus)	0.01	0.02	0.03	NA	NA
Brain (whole)	0.02	0.03	0.03	NA	NA
Brown fat	0.05	0.07	0.24	0.03	NA
Bulbo-urethral gland	0.45	0.74	0.51	0.09	NA
Caecum mucosa	0.17	0.29	0.53	0.10	NA
Cartilage	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
Cerebrospinal fluid	0.78	0.75	1.67	0.16	NA
Choroid plexus	0.52	0.46	0.78	0.08	NA
Colon mucosa	0.17	0.31	0.39	0.08	NA
Dose site	225.55	62.03	6.55	0.79	NA
Epididymis	0.09	0.37	0.44	0.07	NA
Epimysium	0.16	0.18	0.33	0.05	NA
Epithelial tongue	0.21	0.31	0.42	0.06	NA
Exorbital lachrymal gland	0.15	0.19	0.22	0.04	NA
Hair (follicle)	0.10	0.18	0.29	0.04	NA
Hair (tactile)	0.20	0.80	0.74	0.11	NA
Harderian gland	0.13	0.09	0.11	0.05	NA
Intra-orbital lachrymal gland	0.09	0.19	0.15	0.04	NA
Kidney (CM Junction)	0.96	1.77	4.39	0.95	0.04
Kidney cortex	1.00	1.29	2.64	0.49	0.04
Kidney medulla	0.52	0.60	0.69	0.22	NA

Lens	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
Liver	0.33	0.45	0.56	0.08	NA
Lung	0.85	1.22	1.16	0.11	NA
Lymph nodes	0.19	0.27	0.25	0.04	NA
Meninges	0.19	0.38	0.40	0.03	NA
Mucus gland	0.16	0.26	0.54	0.05	NA
Muscle	0.07	0.13	0.19	0.03	NA
Myocardium	0.28	0.37	0.32	0.04	NA
Nasal mucosa	0.27	0.19	0.22	0.04	NA
Oesophageal wall	0.21	0.18	0.55	0.06	NA
Pancreas	0.29	0.30	0.36	0.06	NA
Penis	0.50	0.73	0.49	0.07	NA
Periodontal membrane	0.73	1.02	1.04	0.09	NA
Pineal body	0.17	0.22	0.27	0.05	NA
Pituitary	0.24	0.35	0.32	0.03	NA
Plasma FD1	1.56	2.56	2.16	0.16	0.01
Plasma1	1.57	2.57	2.40	0.44	0.13
Preputial gland	0.08	0.10	0.16	0.05	NA
Prostate	0.17	0.17	0.29	0.04	NA
Salivary glands	0.29	0.33	0.28	0.05	NA
Seminal vesicles	0.06	0.08	0.10	0.02	NA
Skin (non-pigmented)	0.04	0.10	0.22	0.05	NA
Skin (subcutis)	0.12	0.24	0.42	0.11	NA
Small intestine mucosa	0.22	0.26	0.28	NA	NA
Spinal cord	0.02	0.02	0.03	NA	NA
Spleen	NS	0.19	0.19	0.03	NA
Stomach mucosa (fundic)	0.08	0.13	0.30	0.04	NA
Stomach mucosa (non-fundic)	0.10	0.15	0.35	0.06	NA
Testis	0.18	0.32	0.47	0.05	NA
Thymus	0.06	0.12	0.13	0.03	NA
Thyroid	0.43	0.57	0.37	0.15	NA
Tongue	0.18	0.50	0.50	0.10	NA
Tooth pulp	1.18	1.80	2.68	0.21	NA
Trachea	0.22	0.31	0.52	0.07	NA
Urinary bladder wall	0.52	1.48	0.40	0.05	NA
Uveal tract/retina	0.19	0.37	0.64	0.08	NA
Vitreous humour	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
White fat	NA	0.02	0.04	NA	NA

¹Counts determined by liquid scintillation; NA- below limit of quantification; FD – freeze-dried before measurement; NS – not sectioned tissue.

Table S9. Tissue uptake (percentage of injected dose per gram of tissue, %ID/g) from quantitative whole-body autoradiography of [³H]1 after 4, 8, 24, 72 and 168 h of subcutaneous administration (30 nmol/kg). n = 1.

Tissue	% ID /g				
	4 h	8 h	24 h	72 h	168 h
Adrenal cortex	0.05	0.24	0.10	NA	NA
Adrenal medulla	0.26	0.51	0.25	0.03	NA
Aortic wall	0.16	0.16	0.16	NA	NA
Bile ducts	0.77	1.02	0.59	0.08	NA
Blood	0.52	0.74	0.38	0.06	NA
Blood ¹	0.59	0.80	0.52	0.16	0.05
Bone marrow	0.07	0.14	0.08	0.02	NA
Bone mineral	NA	0.02	NA	NA	NA
Bone surface	0.09	0.14	0.11	0.02	NA
Brain (cerebellum)	NA	0.02	NA	NA	NA
Brain (cortex)	NA	0.02	NA	NA	NA
Brain (medulla oblongata)	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
Brain (olfactory bulb)	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
Brain (thalamus)	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
Brain (whole)	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
Brown fat	0.05	0.07	0.05	0.02	NA
Bulbo-urethral gland	0.22	0.32	0.27	0.04	NA
Caecum mucosa	0.06	0.25	0.21	0.03	NA
Cartilage	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
Cerebrospinal fluid	0.32	0.47	0.37	0.05	NA
Choroid plexus	0.34	0.56	0.16	0.03	NA
Colon mucosa	0.05	0.22	0.15	0.03	NA
Dose site	24.43	76.83	6.29	0.19	NA
Epididymis	0.09	0.21	0.20	0.02	NA
Epimysium	0.09	0.24	0.10	0.03	NA
Epithelial tongue	0.08	0.18	0.12	0.02	NA
Exorbital lachrymal gland	0.07	0.13	0.07	NA	NA
Hair (follicle)	0.06	0.11	0.12	NA	NA
Hair (tactile)	0.13	0.44	0.28	0.04	NA
Harderian gland	0.02	0.08	0.03	NA	NA
Intra-orbital lachrymal gland	0.03	0.09	0.05	NA	NA
Kidney (CM Junction)	0.32	0.54	0.79	0.27	NA
Kidney cortex	0.32	0.52	0.59	0.21	NA
Kidney medulla	0.25	0.40	0.18	0.03	NA

Lens	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
Liver	0.18	0.30	0.21	0.04	NA
Lung	0.44	0.72	0.40	0.06	NA
Lymph nodes	0.09	0.36	0.17	0.03	NA
Meninges	0.11	0.10	0.07	NA	NA
Mucus gland	0.08	0.15	0.09	0.03	NA
Muscle	0.04	0.08	0.05	NA	NA
Myocardium	0.12	0.22	0.12	0.02	NA
Nasal mucosa	0.12	0.14	0.06	NA	NA
Oesophageal wall	0.10	0.17	0.18	0.03	NA
Pancreas	0.13	0.21	0.10	0.03	NA
Penis	0.12	0.45	0.27	0.04	NA
Periodontal membrane	0.38	0.48	0.23	0.04	NA
Pineal body	0.07	0.21	0.08	NA	NA
Pituitary	0.08	0.19	0.07	0.02	NA
Plasma FD ¹	0.92	1.30	0.69	0.09	NA
Plasma ¹	0.95	1.26	0.88	0.25	0.06
Preputial gland	0.08	0.26	0.06	0.02	NA
Prostate	0.04	0.19	0.13	NA	NA
Salivary glands	0.13	0.14	0.09	0.02	NA
Seminal vesicles	0.02	0.03	0.03	NA	NA
Skin (non-pigmented)	0.02	0.08	0.08	NA	NA
Skin (subcutis)	0.09	0.22	0.22	0.04	NA
Small intestine mucosa	0.08	0.16	0.10	NA	NA
Spinal cord	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
Spleen	0.07	0.13	0.05	NA	NA
Stomach mucosa (fundic)	0.07	0.10	0.11	0.03	NA
Stomach mucosa (non-fundic)	0.05	0.08	0.08	NA	NA
Testis	0.08	0.22	0.09	0.02	NA
Thymus	0.03	0.06	0.04	NA	NA
Thyroid	0.23	0.19	0.15	0.03	NA
Tongue	0.09	0.23	0.20	0.05	NA
Tooth pulp	0.41	0.77	0.49	0.09	NA
Trachea	0.12	0.15	0.12	0.03	NA
Urinary bladder wall	0.21	0.50	0.27	0.10	NA
Uveal tract/retina	0.09	0.27	0.22	0.04	NA
Vitreous humour	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
White fat	NA	NA	0.02	NA	NA

¹Counts determined by liquid scintillation; NA- below limit of quantification; FD – freeze-dried before measurement.

Table S10. Extraction efficacies of [³H]2 and [³H]1 for metabolite profiling

Peptide tracer	Adm. Route	Time (h)	Recovery (%)
[³H]2	sc	4	95.1
		8	99.2
		24	92.8
		72	92.5
		168	94.9
[³H]1	sc	4	92.8
		8	98.6
		24	84.5
		72	85.6
		168	92.2
[³H]2	iv	0.08	96.8
		2	100.9
		4	96.0
		8	94.1
		24	92.8
		72	94.1
		168	93.9

Figure S1. Correlation between tissue absorption of [³H]1 [³H]2 by QWBA

Figure S1. Correlation between tissue absorptions of [³H]1 and [³H]2 peptides measured by quantitative whole-body autoradiography (QWBA). Each dot represents uptake values in percentage of injected dose per gram of tissue after administration of [³H]2 (Y-axis) or [³H]1 (X-axis) for different time points. Linear regression values are indicated in the graphs, n = 1 for 70 tissue regions.

Figure S2. Comparison of compound distribution in plasma (**1**, **2**) and full blood ($[^3\text{H}]\mathbf{2}$, $[^{89}\text{Zr}]\mathbf{2}$, $[^3\text{H}]\mathbf{1}$) after intravenous or subcutaneous administration.

Figure S2. Concentration is expressed as percentage of the injected dose per gram of tissue (%ID/g) for data obtained from liquid-scintillation counting ($[^3\text{H}]\mathbf{1}$ and $[^3\text{H}]\mathbf{2}$), gamma-counting ($[^{89}\text{Zr}]\mathbf{2}$) and LC-MS quantification (**1** and **2**). Data is plotted as mean \pm SD, $n \geq 5$ ($[^{89}\text{Zr}]\mathbf{2}$, iv and sc), $n = 4$ (**1** and **2**, sc), $n = 3$ (**2**, iv), $n = 1$ (**1**, iv; $[^3\text{H}]\mathbf{2}$, iv and sc). Injected doses are: 30 nmol/kg ($[^3\text{H}]\mathbf{2}$ and $[^3\text{H}]\mathbf{1}$, iv and sc), 20 nmol/kg (**1** and **2**, iv and sc) and 3 nmol/kg ($[^{89}\text{Zr}]\mathbf{2}$).

Figure S3. Metabolic profiling of peptides [^3H]2 and [^3H]1 in rat plasma.

Figure S3. **A.** radio-HPLC analysis of rat plasma after subcutaneous administration of [^3H]1. **B.** radio-HPLC analysis of rat plasma after subcutaneous (top) and intravenous (bottom) administration of [^3H]2. Dashed lines indicate the retention times of the three radioactive metabolites of [^3H]2. Gray bars indicate the retention times of the parent compounds.

Figure S4. Fractionation for metabolite identification of [^3H]2-M3.

Figure S4. Measured radioactivity of each fraction eluted from the HPLC separation of plasma from animals dosed with [^3H]2. The analysed sample was from plasma pooled from animals dosed after 8, 24 and 72 h. No unique MS signals could be identified in fractions B01, B07 and B11. Metabolite [^3H]2-M3 was detected in fraction D03. The parent compound [^3H]2 elutes in fraction C12.

Figure S5. LC-MS-RAD analysis of fraction D03 from [^3H]2 plasma and matrix blank after fractionation

Figure S5. Chromatograms of fraction D03 UPLC analysis from animals dosed with [^3H]2 and matching control. **A.** MS detection of rat plasma from non-dosed animals, full scan, total ion count (TIC). **B.** Liquid scintillation detection of rat plasma from animals dosed with [^3H]2. **C.** MS detection, from animals dosed with [^3H]2, full scan, TIC.

Figure S6. MS spectra of fraction D03 from [^3H]2 plasma and matrix blank after fractionation

Figure S6. A. Combined MS spectra from retention time 25.6-25.9 min of the chromatogram shown in Figure S5C (animals dosed with [^3H]2). **B.** Combined MS spectra from retention time

25.6-25.9 min of the chromatogram shown in Figure S5A (non-dosed control animals). **C.** Zoom in the MS spectra shown in **A** from m/z 1210 to 1253, with the unique envelope at m/z 1221.87 **D.** Zoom in the MS control spectra shown in **B** from m/z 1210 to 1253.

Figure S7. Deconvoluted molecular weight of m/z 1221.87**Figure S7.** Deconvolution of m/z envelope 1221.87 shown in Figure S6C. MaxEnt3 (Waters, USA) algorithm was used.

Figure S8. LC-MS-RAD analysis of [^3H]2 plasma and matrix blank without fractionation

Figure S8. Chromatograms of plasma analysis from animals dosed with [^3H]2 subcutaneously after 24 h and a matching control. **A.** MS detection of rat plasma from non-dosed animals, full scan, total ion count (TIC). **B.** Liquid scintillation detection of rat plasma from animals dosed with [^3H]2. **C.** MS detection, from animals dosed with [^3H]2, full scan, TIC.

Figure S9. MS spectra from the analysis of [^3H]2 plasma and matrix blank without fractionation

Figure S9. A. Combined MS spectra from retention time 28.7-29.0 min of the chromatogram shown in Figure S8A of non-dosed control animals B. Combined MS spectra from retention time 28.7-29.0 min of the chromatogram shown in Figure S8C from animals dosed with [^3H]2. C. Zoom

in the MS spectra shown in **A** from m/z 1197 to 1260. **D.** Zoom in the MS spectra shown in **B** from m/z 1197 to 1260, with the unique envelope at m/z 1221.88

Figure S10. A. Scheme of the metabolism of **2** generating metabolite **2-M3** B. Theoretical envelope containing the $(M+4H)^{+4}$ molecular ion of the non-tritiated metabolite **2-M3** (top) and observed envelope of the metabolite $[^3H]2-M3$ (bottom).

Figure S11: Non-radioactive peptides analytical characterization**Figure S11.** UPLC-UV and MS spectra of non-radioactive peptides. **A.** Left panel: ESI spectrum of purified peptide 1. Most abundant isotope indicated. Calculated Mass (average isotope

composition): 4255.7; $[M+3H]^{3+}$: 1419.6, $[M+4H]^{4+}$: 1064.9. Right panel: UPLC chromatogram of purified **1**, Rt 9.13 min. **B.** Left panel: ESI spectrum of purified peptide **2**. Most abundant isotope indicated. Calculated Mass (average isotope composition): 5311.0; $[M+3H]^{3+}$: 1771.3, $[M+4H]^{4+}$: 1328.8, $[M+5H]^{5+}$: 1063.2. Right panel: UPLC chromatogram of purified **2**, Rt 8.37 min **C.** Left panel: ESI spectrum of purified peptide **3**. Most abundant isotope indicated. Calculated Mass (average isotope composition): 3539.9; $[M + 3H]^{3+}$: 1181.0, $[M + 4H]^{4+}$: 886.0, $[M + 5H]^{5+}$: 709.0. Right panel: UPLC chromatogram of purified **3**, Rt 1.62 min. **D.** Left panel: ESI spectrum of purified peptide **4**. Left panel: ESI spectrum of purified peptide **4**. Most abundant isotope indicated. Calculated Mass (average isotope composition): 4596.1; $[M+3H]^{3+}$: 1533.0, $[M+4H]^{4+}$: 1150.0, $[M+5H]^{5+}$: 920.2. Right panel: UPLC chromatogram of purified **4**, Rt 6.71 min. **E.** Left panel: ESI spectrum of purified peptide **6**. Most abundant isotope indicated. Calculated Mass (average isotope composition): 5223.8; $[M+3H]^{3+}$: 1742.3, $[M+4H]^{4+}$: 1307.0, $[M+5H]^{5+}$: 1045.8. Right panel: UPLC chromatogram of purified **6**, Rt 8.52 min.

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